

Poetry of Al-Mu'tamid bin Abbad and Third Yusuf/ Balancing Study

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
April 16, 2021

Accepted:
June 24, 2021

Keywords :

Sport, Social Systems,
Al-Mu'tamid Bin Abbad

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5027507

Abstract

Sport is a social movement that comes on top of social organizations that have advantages and characteristics that are unique to them from other social systems, and in order for sport to keep pace with and achieve development in various areas of life. The desired state of change, it is necessary to provide and prepare conscious and efficient leaders to manage the sports movement, after the movement has become a wide and comprehensive sports, in which many large groups of community members work and supervise them and are served by large and complex institutions and organizations that require knowledge and awareness of the foundations, functions and methods of achieving the desired goals Through the joint work of individuals in sports institutions.

Introduction

Sports and its delay are largely related to the level of administrative leadership, and in order for institutions and organizations to achieve these goals, it was necessary for the state to organize the sports movement at its various levels with administrative and structural formulas commensurate with nature. The sports movement and the extent of its compatibility with the directives of the state in its philosophy in the political, social and economic fields with the difference of these formulas, size and tasks, what unites them is the fact that sports clubs represent the most important facilities out of all these formulas, as they are considered one of the most prominent institutions within the sports structures in different countries, as the Sports clubs are administrative and social institutions that include many human segments such as members of administrative bodies, players, coaches, staff and fans of the club as fans and supporters of the club's activities such as containing stadiums and gyms, and the club president as an administrative leader is considered the main pillar in the club's management and stands at the head of the club's administrative ladder and sets goals Planning, decision-making, coordination, follow-up and follow-up. Evaluation. The process of promoting the club and raising its level, and why is it sufficient? The administrative role plays a major role in the performance of the sports club, as its evaluation has a significant role in diagnosing the strength and weakness of the sports movement of the sports club.

The importance of the research lies in identifying the performance of the club president from the point of view of the members of the administrative bodies in those sports clubs by making use of his personal, practical and social competencies and benefiting from them in directing the available materials. And the human capabilities to achieve the goals of the club he manages at the lowest possible cost, with reasonable effort and with the best result.

Research problem

The club president is a sports and administrative leader who directs the sports movement in the club and must employ all available social energies in a good and effective manner. And bring about the desired change in the club, which includes different segments of members of the administrative bodies, coaches and players who carry different cultures in order to satisfy their desires to exercise the colors of sports activity. It also includes individuals who have the ability to employ their expertise to develop the sports movement through their training or supervision of sports teams, as well as investing in media, public, social and humanitarian relations, which are reflected in their entirety at the levels. The work and live interaction that the club achieves in relation to the goals of human life and the goals of the sports movement.

The most obvious role of the club president is to act as coordinator of the various activities of the club, monitor the implementation of policies, and take actions and methods to ensure the achievement of the common goal. Despite these executive functions performed by the club president, he cannot assume them alone, but distributes them in the form of competencies and responsibilities to other members of the group, leaving him with general supervision and direction. Social interaction is the basis of every relationship within the group, and is the core of the leadership process.

The members of the club's administrative bodies are considered the most relevant segments to the type of work and the facilities provided to these segments by the club president who are more able than others to evaluate their performance by following up on their work, activities and method of work. Dealt with him. Educational, sports and training processes in the sports club, so the research problem lies in the following question: What are the competencies possessed by the president of the sports club that qualify him to lead the management in it successfully and evaluate it from the point of view of the opinion of his employees from members of the administrative bodies?

Research Objectives

1. Evaluation of the administrative competencies of the heads of Iraqi sports clubs of the first degree for the sports season 2019-2020 AD from the point of view of the members of the administrative bodies of those clubs.
2. Evaluation of the performance of the heads of Iraqi sports clubs of the first degree for the sports season 2019-2020 AD from the point of view of members of the administrative bodies and coaches.

Research areas

- The human field: members of the administrative bodies of the Iraqi sports clubs of the first degree for the sports season 2019-2020.
- Date range: from 20/2/2019 to 15/7/2019.
- The spatial domain: the headquarters of the first-class sports clubs in Iraq.

Search procedures

Research Methodology

The researcher used the descriptive method in the survey method because it is related to the nature of the study.

The research community and its sample

The research community represented the members of the administrative bodies of the Iraqi sports clubs of the first degree, numbering twenty sports clubs, comprising (145) members of the administrative board.

While the research sample (75) members of the administrative board represented (51.7%) of the total research community.

Methods of data collection

The researcher used the following devices and tools:

(Arab and foreign sources and references, personal interviews, a questionnaire to measure the administrative competencies of the manager of an administrative organization from the point of view of his subordinates, a questionnaire for the performance evaluation scale for heads of sports clubs, a. A questionnaire for the individual response to the two scales (International Information Network, the Internet, a questionnaire to unload data for the two scales)

Steps to conduct a search

The researcher used two scales, the first (the scale of administrative competencies for the manager of an administrative organization from the point of view of his subordinates) (1), and the second (the scale of evaluating the performance of sports club heads). (2). the researcher found that the two scales are used and codified on the Arab environment in previous studies, so they were relied upon.

First / The measure of administrative competencies for the manager of the administrative organization from the point of view of his subordinates:

This scale was prepared by (Abdul Bari Durra 1994) (5: 316) and the scale consists of (80) items distributed over (6) axes as follows:

- Axis competencies goals.
- Planning Competencies Center.
- Competence Center for the management of the organization and its employees.
- The focus of competencies social relations.
- Calendar axis.
- The focus of professional growth.

The items on the scale are answered according to three alternatives (always doing the work – sometimes not doing the work) and the weights of the scores for the answers on the scale alternatives (3-2-1) are given respectively, so that the upper limits of the scale scores become (240) Degree and minimum (80). Degree.

Second / Scale for evaluating the performance of sports club heads:

This scale was prepared (WalidKhaledHammam 2004) (44: 7). The scale consists of (45) items distributed on (5) axes as follows:

- Work planning in the gym / 8 paragraphs.
- Organization and management of work in the sports club / 8 paragraphs.
- Public and Human Relations / 10 paragraphs.
- Financial issues / 10 paragraphs.
- Follow-up and evaluation of work in the club / 9 paragraphs.

Scientific bases for the two scales

The researcher was not satisfied with the validity of the two scales, but she extracted the scientific bases for them as follows:

1-The validity of the two scales:

The researcher presented the two scales to professors and experts in the field of management and organization to see their suitability for the study, and they all agreed on the validity of the two scales by (100%), which indicates their enjoyment of the two scales. Content validity.

2-The stability of the two scales:

The researcher calculated the stability of the scale (administrative competencies of a manager of an administrative organization from the point of view of his subordinates) in three ways, namely (testing and re-testing) (Tha'irDawood 2020) (3: 198), and the method (split-half with the Spearman-Brown equation) (Tha'irDawood 2020) (3: 237), and the method (Alpha Cronbach's coefficient) (Tha'irDaoud 2020) (3: 287), applying it to (8).) Members of the administrative body of Al-Sulaikh Sports Club, and they were excluded from the main work sample for the sports season 2019-2020 AD, in (test and retest method) the simple Pearson correlation coefficient was used between the scores of the two applications and the calculated value was (0.874) which has a significant level (Sig) Its value is (0.001), which is smaller than the approved significance level of (0.05), which indicates that the scale has a coefficient of stability. High.

As for the (half-splitting) method, the paragraphs were divided into two groups, the group of paragraphs that carry odd numbers and the group of paragraphs that carry even numbers and by using the Spearman correlation coefficient between the individual scores and even the paragraphs, the researcher obtained the calculated value (0.892), which represents the stability. Corrected by (Spearman-Brown) equation and the stability coefficient of the scale became (0.942), which indicates that the scale has a high stability coefficient. .

The value of (Cronbach's alpha coefficient) for internal consistency was also extracted to identify the extent to which the paragraphs are related to each other within the scale, as well as the correlation of each paragraph with the scale as a whole, and calculated. The value of (0.933) was reached at a significance level (Sig) of (0.000) which is less than the approved significance level of (0.05), which indicates that the scale has a high stability coefficient.

As for the stability of the scale (evaluating the performance of the heads of sports clubs) it was also calculated by three methods: (test and re-test), method (Rolon half equation) and method (Cronbach's alpha coefficient) and was applied to the same sample. In the (test and retest method) the calculated value reached (0.856), which has a significance level (Sig) of (0.000), which is less than the approved significance level of (0.05), which indicates that the scale has a high stability coefficient. By correcting it (Spearman-Brown), the scale's stability coefficient became (0.913), which indicates that the scale has a high stability coefficient, and the value of (Cronbach's alpha coefficient) was extracted for internal consistency and its calculated value was (0.928) at the level of significance (Sig) of (0.000) which is less than the approved significance level of (0.05), which indicates that the scale has a high coefficient of stability.

Main Research Experience

The researcher conducted the main experiment on 3/1/2019 by distributing scales forms (administrative competencies of the manager of an administrative organization from the point of view of his subordinates, and evaluating the performance of sports club heads) to (75) members. The administrative bodies of the Iraqi sports clubs are of the highest degree. The first for the 2019-2020 sports season.

Statistical Laws

The software (IBM SPSS Statistic Ver25) was used to extract the following: (arithmetic mean, standard deviation, coefficient of deviation, Pearson correlation coefficient, Rolon equation, Spearman-Brown corrected correlation coefficient, Cronbach's alpha coefficient, single sample T-test.)

Presentation and discussion of the results

For the purpose of the research objectives and interpretation of the results, the researcher processed the data statistically according to the objectives of her study as follows:

Presentation and discussion of the first objective

After collecting and unpacking the data, the data were statistically processed for the administrative competency assessment scale for the heads of Iraqi sports clubs of the first degree for the 2019-2020 sports season from the point of view of the members of those administrative bodies. As shown in Table No. (1)

Table (1)

Statistical controls for administrative competencies by axes for heads of Iraqi sports clubs
From the point of view of the members of the administrative bodies

indication	Sig	value (t)	degree of freedom	hypothetical mean	+A	<u>S</u>	Axis
moral	0.000	41.45	74	14	1.16	19.58	Goals competencies
moral	0.000	15.68	74	18	3.02	23.47	Planning Competencies
moral	0.001	15.05	74	20	2.95	25.12	Work management

							competencies
moral	0.000	6.46	74	12	2.77	14.07	Social Relationship Competencies
moral	0.003	9.41	74	16	2.33	18.53	Sufficient follow-up and evaluation of work
moral	0.000	2.08	74	12	2.72	12.66	Adequate professional growth

It is clear from Table No. (1) That the arithmetic mean value of the responses of the members of the administrative bodies to the paragraphs of the axis (objective competencies) amounted to (19.58), with a standard deviation of (1.16).) And when testing the significance of differences between the mean scores of the sample and the hypothetical mean of the axis (14) using a one-sample t-test, the calculated value of (T) was (41.45), and the p-value and its symbol (Sig) of (0.000) is smaller than the value The approved amount of (0.05), which indicates that it is statistically significant, that is, the difference is significant in favor of the research sample.

The researcher believes that the opinion of the administrators regarding the competency objectives of the heads of their clubs indicates that the heads of sports clubs have good capabilities in this axis in terms of clearly defining the goals and working to achieve them in line with the local environment data and the capabilities of the sports club. The researcher's conclusion is consistent with what was stated (Abdul Hamid Sharaf 1997) that "the clarity of the goal makes it easy to devise clear and specific purposes that are also suitable for achieving these purposes through the departments and sections of the state." the sports institution until the general objective previously set by the higher management is achieved" (6:72)

It is also noted from the table the results of the sample answers on the axis (planning competencies) that the arithmetic mean of the value of the answers of the members of the administrative bodies amounted to (23.47) and with a standard deviation of (3.02), and when testing the significance of the differences between the mean scores of the sample and the hypothetical average of the axis (18)) Using the T-test for one sample, the calculated value of (T) equaled (15.68), and the significance level (Sig) value of (0.000) is less than the approved value of (0.05), which indicates that it is statistically significant, that is, the difference is significant in favor of The research sample.

The researcher believes that the opinion of administrators in the axis of competency planning for the heads of their clubs indicates that the heads of sports clubs have good capabilities in this axis in terms of clearly defining goals and working to achieve them in line with the data of the local environment and the capabilities of the sports club. It was pointed out by (TimurJayi 2001) "Planning is the faithful guardian of the goals of any plan. It focuses on these goals in general or procedural goals, and focuses attention on them, protecting them from loss or neglect" (2:44)

It also notes that the results of the sample answers on the axis (work management competencies) that the arithmetic mean value of the answers of the members of the administrative bodies amounted to (25.12) and the standard deviation (2.95) when testing the significance of the differences between the mean scores of the sample and the hypothetical average of the axis (20) Using a one-sample T test. The (calculated) value is (15.05), and the significance level (Sig) value of (0.001) is less than the approved value of (0.05), which indicates that it is statistically significant, that is, the difference is significant in favor of the research sample.

The researcher believes that the opinion of administrators about the competencies of the work management of the heads of their clubs indicates that the heads of sports clubs have good potentials in this axis in terms of clearly defining goals and working to achieve them in line with. The data of the local environment and the capabilities of the sports club, so that the result reached by the researcher was identical. With a study (TimurJayi 2001)

It also notes that the results of a sample of answers on the axis (competencies of social relations) that the arithmetic average value for the answers of members of administrative bodies was (14.07), with a standard deviation (2.77), and the calculated value of (t) reached (6.46), and the value of the level of significance (Sig) for (0.000) is smaller than the approved value of (0.05), which indicates that it is significant, that is, the difference is in favor of the research sample.

The researcher believes that the opinion of administrators regarding the competencies of the social relations of the heads of their clubs indicates that the heads of sports clubs have good capabilities in this axis in terms of clearly defining goals and working to achieve them in line with the data of the local environment and the capabilities of the sports club, that the result reached by the researcher is identical. With a study (RasheedHamdoun 2001) "The club presidents are considered the cornerstone of the administrative process because they lead the educational and educational process in the club and participate in these very important tasks. They lead the generations on which the nation will depend to build the future. Their behavior is to follow the established traditions of sporting life as a practice that the athletes learn in the club and pass on to the community" (4:196)

The results of the sample answers on the axis (adequacy of follow-up and evaluation of work) indicated that the arithmetic mean of the arithmetic value of the answers of members of the administrative bodies was (18.53), with a standard deviation of (18.53). 2.33, and the calculated value of (T) was (9.41), and the significance level value (Sig) which is (0.003) is smaller than the approved value (0.05), which indicates that it is significant, ie. The difference is significant in favor of the research sample.

The researcher believes that the opinion of the administrators on the adequacy of following up and evaluating the work of the heads of their clubs indicates the awareness of the research sample of the heads of sports clubs who have good potential in this axis in terms of clarity. Defining goals and working to achieve them in line with the data of the local environment and the capabilities of the sports club, so that the result is that the results of the researcher are consistent with what was confirmed by the study (RasheedHamdoun 2001) "confirming the validity of the results reached by the researcher. The importance of this axis in the administrative work in the sports club (4:223)

It also notes the results of the sample answers on the axis (adequacy of professional growth) that the arithmetic mean value of the answers of members of the administrative bodies amounted to (12.66) and the standard deviation (2.72) and the calculated value. From (t) it reached (2.08), and the significance level value (Sig) which is (0.000) is less than the approved value of (0.05), which indicates that it is significant, that is, the difference is significant in favor of the research sample.

The researcher believes that the opinion of the administrators regarding the adequacy of the professional growth of the heads of their clubs indicates that the heads of sports clubs have good potentials in this axis in terms of clearly defining goals and working to achieve them in line with. Data of the local environment and the capabilities of the sports club. Study (Peter. F. 1995) "The foundation of effective leadership is to think through, define and establish the club's mission in a clear and clear way that loses and maintains goals, priorities and standards at work" (1: 187)

Conclusions and recommendations

Conclusions

1. The heads of sports clubs possess the administrative competencies that qualify him to carry out his work from the point of view of the administrators.
2. That the heads of sports clubs possess the administrative skills represented in competencies (goals, work management in the sports club, social relations, follow-up and work evaluation) from the point of view of administrators.
3. The opinions of the administrative bodies in their evaluation of the administrative competencies coincided with the level of performance of the heads of their sports clubs.
4. The opinions of the administrators were identical in their evaluation of the level of performance of the heads of their sports clubs.
5. Possession of club heads with administrative competencies qualifies them to obtain a positive evaluation from the point of view of the administrators.

Recommendations

1. Conducting a periodic evaluation of the administrative competencies of the heads of Iraqi sports clubs.
2. Emphasis on the mental leadership skills of the club president (drawing strategies, setting plans and goals, and organizing administrative work compared to human and technical skills)
3. The necessity of involving club heads in development courses to increase their administrative competencies.
4. Holding regular seminars and meetings between the club president and members of the administrative bodies to discuss their needs and problems and try to overcome them.
5. Giving members of the administrative bodies' sufficient freedom to exercise their leadership role in working within the sports club.

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